

Innovation in Sustainability: Addressing Heat Exchange Problems through Nano-biomaterial Simulations

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Amid the growing global climate crisis, finding innovative and sustainable solutions to mitigate heat-related problems has become a pressing concern. It is crucial that we explore unconventional materials and approaches to address these challenges. In this article, I would like to share my own experiences using nano-biomaterials, particularly clay type, as a viable and environmentally friendly solution to combat heat-related problems in homes and industries.

The Heat Dilemma

Rising temperatures and extreme weather events are becoming increasingly common around the world. The greenhouse effect, caused by the basin where our capital is located, has made our rural cities, such as Chillán, especially vulnerable. The consequences include discomfort, increased energy consumption for refrigeration, and even serious health risks.

Average weekly temperature in the city of Chillán, 2023¹

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¹ hikersbay.com. (n.d.). Chillán: weather - average temperatures in the day and at night, sunny and cloudy days. Annual rainfall and snowfall in Chillán. <https://hikersbay.com/climate/chile/chillan?lang=en>

The Potential of Nano-biomaterials

Traditional building materials, such as concrete and asphalt, contribute significantly to urban heat. These materials absorb and emit heat, exacerbating the urban heat basin effect. However, nano-biomaterials offer a promising alternative. One of these is nanoparticle clays, which, according to my preliminary studies, have great potential to dethrone the origin of the greenhouse effect: expanded polystyrene.

Maximum temperature anomalies, March 2023 report²

My Experience with Clay-Based Nano-biomaterials

As a researcher and environmental enthusiast, I embarked on a journey to study the potential of clay-based nano-biomaterials to address problems related to heat transfer. This I discovered:

1. Natural Cooling Properties: Nanoparticle clays possess excellent thermal properties that can help regulate indoor temperatures. It has a high thermal resistance, according to the density that is provided. This means that it can absorb and retain heat during the day and release it slowly at night, keeping indoor spaces cooler.

2. Sustainable and Available: Nanoparticle clays are abundant and environmentally friendly. They require a minimal amount of energy for extraction and processing, making it a sustainable option with the high-energy expenditure in production of their counterparts.

² Crespo Fuentes, J., Lobos Ortega, E., Moya Caro, A., & Reyes Kohler, A. (2021). Boletín Climatológico: Vol 84 N°. In <https://bibliotecadigital.ciren.cl/> (ISSN 0716-2073). Dirección Meteorológica de Chile. <https://bibliotecadigital.ciren.cl/bitstream/handle/20.500.13082/32975/boletin-04-2021.pdf>

3. Improved Aesthetics: Clay-based nano-biomaterials can also be molded into various architectural forms and designs, enhancing the aesthetics of urban spaces.

Thermal analysis of starch-chitosan films (a) without and (b) with nano clay. 1) Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), 2) Differential Thermogravimetry (TGD) and 3) Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) ³

Challenges and Future Perspectives

While clay-based nano-biomaterials have great potential, there are also challenges to overcome. These include further studies related to their thermal properties, comparing their results with finite element modeling, developing standardized building practices, and educating professionals and the public about the benefits of these materials.

Future prospects for nano-biomaterials in mitigating problems related to heat resistance are promising. Researchers, engineers, and policymakers increasingly recognize the importance of sustainable materials in urban planning. Initiatives and projects that incorporate nano-biomaterials such as clay must be made known to the public, unions, professionals, and public entities; provided that progress is in line with the goals committed by Chile in the United Nations 2030 plan.

³ Aguirre-Loredo, R. Y., Fonseca-García, A., Calambas, H. L., Salazar, A., & Caicedo, C. (2023). Improvements of thermal and mechanical properties of achira starch/chitosan/clay nanocomposite films. *Heliyon*, 9(6), e16782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16782>

The big gap in the global plan for 2030

Global greenhouse gas emission scenario trajectories, gigatonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂e), 2015 to 2030.

Global greenhouse gas emissions scenario trajectories, gigatons of carbon dioxide equivalent, 2015 to 2023⁴

Final Remarks

In a world where climate change poses increasing threats, it is comforting to know that innovative solutions are at our fingertips. My experience with clay-based nano-biomaterials has shown me that we can use nature's gifts to combat the challenges of a warming world. By adopting sustainable materials such as nanoparticle clay and promoting its adoption in construction and urban planning; We can pave the way to cooler, greener and more comfortable cities for future generations.

It's too late to meet climate goals, but let's not give up. Let's work together to make sustainability a cornerstone of our cityscapes and an enduring legacy for our planet.

⁴ King, A. (n.d.). If all 2030 climate targets are met, the planet will heat by 2.7°C this century. That's not OK. The Conversation. <https://theconversation.com/if-all-2030-climate-targets-are-met-the-planet-will-heat-by-2-7-this-century-thats-not-ok-170458>